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Investigating Orbital Debris Mitigation Regime Development In the United States

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the orbital debris mitigation regimes administered by the Federal Communications Commission (FCC), the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). It explores the statutory foundations that empower each agency's regulatory authority and assesses how their respective mission-authorisation processes address or exacerbate gaps in the United States' approach to debris management. The current fragmented framework, spread across multiple agencies with overlapping jurisdictions, has created inefficiencies and regulatory blind spots, undermining effective mitigation as space becomes increasingly congested. While the FCC has updated its licensing requirements and the FAA and NOAA have proposed targeted rules on launch-vehicle disposal and remote-sensing activities, respectively, these measures remain piecemeal. The article argues that a unified, streamlined mission-authorisation framework, aligned with international best practice and treaty obligations, is essential to ensure regulatory clarity, foster interagency collaboration, and incentivise innovation. By prioritising a cohesive debris-mitigation regime, the United States can safeguard orbital sustainability and maintain its leadership in the global space economy.

KEYWORDS: orbital debris, regulatory fragmentation, mission authorisation, interagency coordination, space sustainability

1. INTRODUCTION: THE PROBLEM OF ORBITAL DEBRIS

The commercial space industry is expanding at a rapid pace, driven by innovative technological developments and a thriving economic environment. McKinsey & Company estimates that the global space economy will be worth \$1.8 trillion by 2035, up from \$630 billion in 2023.² This growth is exciting for the future of the commercial space industry, but it also brings a significant challenge: the rapid proliferation of orbital debris in outer space. This poses challenges for the sustainable use of our final frontier by endangering both operational space systems and humans in orbit, creating interference in the collection of vital data, and increasing situations that present risks to national security. As this risk grows, it is timely and of great importance to examine how regulatory bodies administer policies and laws to mitigate such risks in order to foster a sustainable outer space environment for present and future generations. However,

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² McKinsey & Company. (2024, April 8). Space: The \$1.8 trillion opportunity for global economic growth, para 1. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/aerospace-and-defense/our-insights/space-the-1-point-8-trillion-dollar-opportunity-for-global-economic-growth>

the regulatory framework for orbital debris mitigation in the United States is fragmented across multiple federal agencies, which creates an inefficient regulatory environment that not only obstructs the growth of the commercial space industry in the U.S. but also incentivizes foreign companies to take their business elsewhere.

This article seeks to explore the orbital debris mitigation regimes of the Federal Communications Commission (FCC), the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Specifically, it examines the statutory authorities underpinning each agency's regulatory powers and, in doing so, aims to forecast the trajectory of the United States' orbital debris mitigation regime and provide commentary on mission authorization as a crucial measure to address these regulatory gaps in the United States.

1.1 Orbital Debris 101

Orbital debris are a result of collisions between various space objects, including non-functional satellites, spent rocket stages, as well as fragments from collisions or disintegration. The Kessler Syndrome, first proposed by NASA scientist Donald Kessler (and co-authored by Burton Cour-Palais), describes a cascading effect where debris collisions generate even more debris, exponentially increasing the risk to operational spacecraft.³ Kessler and Courpalais' seminal 1978 work noted that this upward trend of collisions could hinder humanity's future space ambitions and activities, even predicting that satellite collisions would become a source of space junk by the year 2000, if not sooner.⁴ This debris endangers operational space systems, interferes with the collection of vital data, and presents risks to national security. According to the Aerospace Corporation, "[a] piece of space debris the size of a blueberry can create the impact of a falling anvil."⁵ This has tremendous implications for establishing a long-term, sustainable presence in low earth orbit (LEO) and beyond. Astronauts aboard the International Space Station (ISS), for example, had to perform multiple orbital maneuvers to avoid debris collisions that reach speeds of up to 22,000 miles per hour. In March 2023, ISS astronauts were forced to fire thrusters twice within an eight-day period to avoid projected collisions, and in the previous year, the ISS maneuvered three times to avoid high-probability collisions, which were a result from the 2020 breakup of a Russian Fregat upper stage tank.⁶ For context, between 1999-2011, the mean amount of times the ISS was forced to maneuver to avoid a collision an average of once per year. However, between 2012-2024 the mean increased to 2.25, representing more than double the number of avoidance maneuvers that occurred within the last twelve years.⁷

These incidents highlight the urgent need for robust regulatory frameworks, ensuring not only safety for current operations, but also the long-term viability of future space activities. With the increasing threat of permanent harm to both space infrastructure and humans in orbit, governments should aim to promulgate

³ Wall, M. (2022, July 14). Kessler Syndrome and the space debris problem. Space.com, para 6. <https://www.space.com/kessler-syndrome-space-debris>

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ Aerospace Corporation. (n.d.). *Space debris 101*. Retrieved from <https://aerospace.org/article/space-debris-101>

⁶ *National Aeronautics and Space Administration*. (2023, June). *Orbital Debris Quarterly News* (p. 2). NASA Orbital Debris Program Office. <https://orbitaldebris.jsc.nasa.gov/quarterly-news/pdfs/odqnv27i2.pdf>

⁷ Note that between the years 2004-2007, 2013, and 2016-2019, there were either no reported data points or there were zero avoidance measures taken. See, Pare, S. (2024, November 26). *ISS dodges its 39th piece of potentially hazardous space junk*. LiveScience. <https://www.livescience.com/space/space-exploration/iss-dodges-its-39th-piece-of-potentially-hazardous-space-junk-experts-say-it-wont-be-the-last>

regulations that not only reduce the current volume of debris, but also places limits on future debris generation.

2. REGULATORY OVERLAP

The United States' regulatory framework for orbital debris is spread across multiple federal agencies, leading to the issue of overlapping jurisdictions and potential inefficiencies that hinder the fluid development of the commercial space industry. The White House, the National Space Council, and the Senate Commerce Committee have all proposed mission authorization frameworks to fill regulatory gaps and streamline oversight. However, the current system ultimately remains fragmented. The FCC has positioned itself as taking the lead in orbital debris mitigation regulation for operational satellite telecommunications, while other federal agencies contribute in other specialized areas: the FAA regulates launch and reentry, NOAA oversees private remote sensing, and NASA provides policy recommendations and guidelines grounded in science.

3. FCC ORBITAL DEBRIS MITIGATION FRAMEWORK

The FCC's involvement in orbital debris mitigation stems from its broader mandate to regulate communications. The *Communications Satellite Act of 1962*⁸ established the FCC's authority over satellite communications, providing a foundation for its role in orbital debris mitigation.⁹ The FCC's statutory authority is grounded in its ability to license satellite operators and ensure compliance with technical and operational standards.

In 2004, the FCC concluded that Section 307(a) of the Communications Act, which mandates licensing radio communications in the "public convenience, interest, or necessity," granted it sufficient authority to adopt orbital debris mitigation requirements.¹⁰ The FCC's interpretation of 307(a) centers around the fact that its orbital debris mitigation rules would serve to advance the Communications Act because orbital debris as a phenomenon affects the cost, reliability, continuity, and safety of satellite operations and the services they provide. Furthermore, broadening the scope of its de facto jurisdictional authority would enable the FCC to promote the effective use of radio in the public interest as per its statutory mandate.¹¹ Thus, the FCC's interpretation of Section 307(a) indicates that its licensing framework for communication satellite activities necessarily should address debris control and prevention.¹²

Building on this interpretation, the FCC proactively took measures to advance orbital debris rulemaking in 2020 and again in 2022 by releasing updated rules to address orbital debris explicitly.¹³ The 2020 rules require satellite operators to submit debris mitigation plans as part of their licensing applications, and the

⁸ Satellite Communications Act of 1962, Pub. L. No. 87-624, 76 Stat. 419 (codified as amended in scattered sections of 47 U.S.C.).

⁹ Harbert, M., & Balakrishnan, A. (2023, Summer). Why space debris flies through regulatory gaps. *Issues in Science and Technology*, para. 3. <https://issues.org/space-debris-fcc-harbert-balakrishnan/#0>

¹⁰ Brown, L., & Stimers, P. (2023, November 6). The FCC's authority in regulating orbital debris. *The Space Review*, para 7. <https://www.thespacereview.com/article/4687/1>

¹¹ Kensing, K., Duall, S., & Persaud, S. (2005, April 18–20). The United States Federal Communications Commission's regulations concerning mitigation of orbital debris. In D. Danesy (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 4th European Conference on Space Debris* (ESA SP-587, p. 571). ESA/ESOC. <https://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/2005ESASP.587..571K>

¹² U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, *Orbiting Debris: A Space Environmental Problem-Background Paper*, OTA-BP-ISC-72 (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1990), Appendix C. <https://ota.fas.org/reports/9033.pdf>

¹³ *Supra* note 10, para. 9.

updated 2022 rules require satellites ending their mission in or passing through Low Earth Orbit (LEO) to deorbit as soon as is practical and no more than five years following mission completion—a significant reduction from the previous post-mission deorbiting guideline of 25 years.¹⁴

Since the FCC exercises oversight over the operation of telecommunications satellites, and since most satellites require part of the radio spectrum to transmit data and information from space, the FCC has effectively become the *de facto* debris regulator for satellite operators.¹⁵ However, despite the agency's proactive measures to address orbital debris, its approach and use of such authority has thus far sparked controversy. While its updated rules provide a framework for debris mitigation, critics argue that the FCC's actions exceed its statutory authority because it has been unilaterally adjudicating regulations on this topic. While a broad jurisdictional authority allows the FCC to act quickly, critics view such actions as conflicting with broader administration policies, lacking coordination with other agencies, or acting presumptively ahead of a coordinated administration position.¹⁶

The FCC's *de facto* authority has been established over time through various rulemaking and case determinations with orbital debris as the core issue. In 2022, for example, the U.S. appeals court (D.C. Cir) denied ViaSat's attempt to force an environmental review on SpaceX based on the statutory requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA).¹⁷ It should be noted here that the court denied ViaSat's appeal based on Article III standing requirements, not on the merits of its NEPA argument. However, in the context of NEPA, it will be interesting to see how opponents of the FCC's regulatory framework for orbital debris exploit NEPA's environmental review requirements as a sword against regulating agencies since it requires federal agencies to consider the environmental impact of their actions before making decisions. While the application of NEPA has never been used in the context of outer space thus far, entities may turn to it in light of the proliferation of orbital debris. Whether NEPA applies to the outer space environment is, however, a question this article does not address.¹⁸

Subsequently, in 2023, the FCC took its first space debris enforcement action against DISH for failing to move its EchoStar-7 satellite to the proper disposal orbit at the satellite's end-of-life as required by DISH's license terms and conditions, further underscoring its *de facto* authority in this domain.¹⁹ Despite these rulings, the recent *Loper Bright Enterprises v. Raimondo* case struck down the Chevron deference and effectively ended federal agencies' ability to interpret ambiguities in the laws they enforced with greater latitude. In the aftermath of the *Loper Bright* decision, it is now of the utmost importance that the regulatory ambiguity and overlap amongst federal agencies be resolved so as to ensure a clear and cohesive framework for addressing orbital debris going forward.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Supra* note 9, para. 16.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ Rainbow, J. (2024, September 16). Connecting the dots: FCC's space sustainability authority in question as need grows. SpaceNews, para 7. <https://spacenews.com/connecting-the-dots-fcc-space-sustainability-authority-question-need-grows/>

¹⁸ *A Sky Full of Stars: Should ViaSat, Inc. v. FCC. Change the Agency's Treatment of Satellites as a Categorical Exclusion Under the National Environmental Policy Act* by Morgan Armstrong.

¹⁹ Federal Communications Commission. (2023, October 2). In the matter of DISH Operating L.L.C. (DA 23-888). <https://docs.fcc.gov/public/attachments/DA-23-888A1.pdf>

4. FAA'S ORBITAL DEBRIS MITIGATION FRAMEWORK

The FAA, under the Department of Transportation (DOT), licenses commercial launch and reentry vehicles, as well as commercial spaceports.²⁰ In 1984, the Office of Commercial Space Transportation (AST) was established as a part of the DOT and in 1995, it was subsequently integrated into the FAA as its only space related line of business.²¹ The FAA addresses orbital debris in commercial space launch activities through licensing and enforcement, research and standards development, and setting financial responsibility and risk allocation requirements.²²

It's authority for regulating orbital debris is derived from the Commercial Space Launch Act of 1984, as codified and amended at 51 U.S.C., which specifically authorizes the Department of Transportation, and consequently, the FAA, "to oversee, license, and regulate commercial launch and reentry activities, and the operation of launch and reentry sites as carried out by the United States (U.S.) citizens or within the United States."²³ In terms of its mission review process and launch license application evaluation, the FAA examines each proposed commercial launch to ensure that no other activities occurring in space are directly at risk. Furthermore, an interagency review of the application, including input from NASA and the Department of Defence (DOD), assists in this process.²⁴

Over the years, the FAA has developed regulations that seek to mitigate the threat posed by orbital debris in several ways. In 14 C.F.R. Part 415.39, the FAA requires expendable launch vehicle (ELV) launch license applicants to demonstrate compliance with §417.129 for any proposed launch of a launch vehicle with a stage or component that will reach Earth orbit. §417.129²⁵ requires applicants to demonstrate that: (1) there is no unplanned physical contact between the vehicle or any of its components and the payload after payload separation; (2) debris generation does not result from the conversion of energy sources into energy that fragments the vehicle or its components, and (3) for all vehicle stages or components that are left in orbit, stored energy is removed by depleting residual fuel and leaving all fuel line valves open, venting any pressurized system, leaving all batteries in a permanent discharge state, and removing any remaining source of stored energy.²⁶ In addition to Part 415.39, 14 C.F.R Part 431.43 specifies that the first two requirements of §417.129 apply to reusable launch and reentry vehicles, and further requires a reusable vehicle operator to perform a collision avoidance analysis to ensure a 200-kilometer separation between the vehicle and an inhabitable orbiting object during launch and reentry.²⁷ Lastly, 14 C.F.R. Part 440, Appendix A, requires launch license applicants seeking a maximum probable loss determination for their activities to share with the FAA, an analysis of the risks posed by launch vehicles to operational satellites in orbit.²⁸

In September of 2023, the FAA released a Notice of Proposed Rulemaking (NPRM) to mitigate the risk posed to the public by uncontrolled disposals, which are situations where satellites reenter Earth's

²⁰ *Commercial Space: Federal Regulation, Oversight, and Utilization*, Congressional Research Service, November 29, 2018, pg. 1. <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/space/R45416.pdf>

²¹ Federal Aviation Administration. (2025, March 20). *About the Office of Commercial Space Transportation*, para 1. https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast

²² *U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, Orbiting Debris: A Space Environmental Problem-Background Paper, OTA-BP-ISC-72* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1990), Appendix C.

²³ Mitigation Methods for Launch Vehicle Upper Stages on the Creation of Orbital Debris, 88 Fed. Reg. 65835 (proposed Sept. 26, 2023) (to be codified at 14 C.F.R. pts. 401, 404, 415, 417, 431, 43, 437, 450, 453).

²⁴ *U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment, Orbiting Debris: A Space Environmental Problem-Background Paper, OTA-BP-ISC-72* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, September 1990), Appendix C.

²⁵ Note that 14 C.F.R. Part 450, §450.171 lists the same requirements as §417.129.

²⁶ 14 C.F.R. § 417.129 (2006).

²⁷ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002). *Launch Activity and Orbital Debris Mitigation: Second Quarter 2002 Quarterly Launch Report* (p. 11). https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/q22002.pdf

²⁸ *Id.*

atmosphere without using propulsion to control its descent.²⁹ The FAA's proposed regulations would require commercial launch providers to dispose of upper stages from their launches in an effort to mitigate the growth of orbital debris.³⁰ Specifically, in the NPRM, the FAA asserted that operators could meet this requirement by performing one of five disposal options that must be performed within 30 days of mission completion: (1) controlled disposal, (2) maneuver to a disposal orbit, (3) maneuver to an Earth-escape orbit, (4) retrieve the debris within 5 years of mission completion, or (5) perform atmospheric uncontrolled disposal or natural decay within 25 years.³¹ As of April 2025, the FAA has not yet issued a final rule, but plans to finalize and publish it sometime in 2025.³²

5. NOAA APPROACH TO ORBITAL DEBRIS MITIGATION

NOAA's role in orbital debris mitigation is linked to its broader mandate to regulate remote sensing. The National and Commercial Space Programs Act (51 U.S.C. Subtitle VI)³³ provides NOAA with explicit statutory authority to oversee commercial remote sensing activities. Under 51 U.S. Code § 60121, NOAA regulates the operation of commercial remote sensing satellites and consequently, maintains the indirect statutory authority to promulgate debris mitigation regulations. § 60121(b) mandates that NOAA comply with any applicable international obligations and national security concerns of the United States. Effectively, this means that NOAA, in regulating commercial remote sensing, must comply with the U.S.'s obligations as outlined in the OST and the Liability Convention.

NOAA's jurisdiction is further limited by 15 CFR Part 960. For example, §960.2(b) states: "a system that contains only such instruments³⁴ will not require a Commerce license," and effectively excludes those instruments used primarily for mission assurance or other technical purposes from NOAA's oversight.³⁵ NOAA's existing statutory authority has led to debates about the agency's future role in orbital debris mitigation and the need for expanded authority, which is particularly consequential in the context of a booming international commercial satellite industry and the need for the U.S. to maintain an attractive regulatory environment for both domestic and foreign satellite companies. Indeed, a recent Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) publication noted that "providing regulatory clarity and certainty through a comprehensive mission authorization framework will encourage increased investment and innovation in space."³⁶

5.1 Policy Developments and Challenges

NOAA's role in orbital debris mitigation has evolved alongside the growth of the commercial space industry. The agency has continued to align its regulations with broader national policies, such as NASA's Orbital Debris Mitigation Standard Practices (ODMSP) and the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination

²⁹ Mitigation Methods *supra* note 41.

³⁰ Foust, J. (2023, September 21). *FAA proposes rule to limit lifetime of upper stages in orbit*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/faa-proposes-rule-to-limit-lifetime-of-upper-stages-in-orbit/>

³¹ Mitigation Methods *supra* note 41.

³² Foust, J. (2024, September 8). *FAA to complete orbital debris upper stage regulations in 2025*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/faa-to-complete-orbital-debris-upper-stage-regulations-in-2025/>

³³ National and Commercial Space Programs Act, Pub. L. No. 111-314, 124 Stat. 3328 (2010).

³⁴ "Instruments" are defined as: [those] used primarily for mission assurance purposes or other technical purposes are not considered remote sensing instruments under this final rule.

³⁵ National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Commercial Remote Sensing Regulatory Affairs. (2022, April 1). *Policy Guidance: Mission assurance (Guidance Circular No. 960.2-1)*. https://www.space.commerce.gov/wp-content/uploads/Guidance_-_Mission-Assurance-040122.pdf

³⁶ Swope, C. (2023, December 20). *Mission authorization: Decoding the space policy dilemma*. CSIS, para 12. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/mission-authorization-decoding-space-policy-dilemma>

Committee (IADC)³⁷ guidelines. However, its limited statutory authority to private remote sensing has curbed its ability to address the full spectrum of debris mitigation challenges.

Early on, the Commercial Remote Sensing Regulatory Affairs (CRSRA) made concerted efforts to develop orbital debris mitigation regulations. From 2000 to 2020, CRSRA (pronounced *kris-rah*) required companies applying for a private remote sensing license to submit a disposal and orbital debris mitigation plan; however after updating its regulations in 2020, that requirement was subsequently eliminated.³⁸ Instead, CRSRA decided to defer to FCC license requirements for orbital debris and spacecraft disposal in order to avoid duplicative regulation.³⁹ Subsequently, in 2024, it began soliciting public comments regarding potential new instructions on the disposal of on-orbit satellites with the purpose of mitigating orbital debris pertaining to subsection (b)(4)'s license requirement of the Land Remote Sensing Act of 1992 (e.g. 51 U.S.C. chapter 601).⁴⁰ Specifically, CRSRA sought "information from interested parties regarding the condition in every CRSRA license requiring the disposal of on orbit spacecraft in a matter satisfactory to the President," and that such information was "necessary to inform CRSRA's approach to providing additional guidance or initiating a narrow rulemaking pertaining to its disposal condition."⁴¹

A growing challenge that CRSRA has seen in recent years is the increasing number of multinational providers of remote sensing systems choosing to obtain radiofrequency licenses from other countries while simultaneously seeking a private remote sensing license in the U.S.⁴² An overarching question to this trend is whether these foreign licenses are sufficiently meeting U.S. standards of orbital debris mitigation. It is important to note that the U.S.'s standard is tied to its international obligations under the 1967 Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (OST), requires state parties to the treaty maintain an authorization and supervision (regulatory) framework.⁴³ This means that it is effectively a state's responsibility to both provide authorization for its commercial space activities and subsequently regulate them, including any regulation of orbital debris. Specifically, a state must bear responsibility for damages to other member states resulting from national space activities.⁴⁴ However, the fragmented nature of U.S. regulatory authority has made it difficult to ensure comprehensive oversight of these obligations in practice.

³⁷ The IADC Guidelines are developed and maintained by the IADC, an international forum of space agencies and authorized governmental or intergovernmental entities to "exchange information on space debris research activities between member space agencies, to facilitate opportunities for co-operation in space debris research, to review the progress of ongoing co-operative activities and to identify debris mitigation options." The most recent update to these guidelines was published in January 2025. *See Comm. on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, Sci. & Tech. Subcomm., IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines, U.N. Doc. A/AC.105/C.1/2025/CRP.9 (Feb. 3, 2025).* https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_12025crp/aac_105c_12025crp_9_0.html/AC_105_C1_2025_CRP09E.pdf

³⁸ *Request for information: Private remote sensing satellite disposal and debris mitigation.* (2024, March 8). Federal Register, 89 Fed. Reg. 13652. <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2024/03/08/2024-05004/request-for-information-private-remote-sensing-satellite-disposal-and-debris-mitigation>

³⁹ *Ibid.*

⁴⁰ Edwards, J. (2024, March 8). NOAA Office of Space Commerce's CRSRA Division seeks input on satellite disposal, debris mitigation regulations. ExecutiveGov, para 1. <https://executivegov.com/2024/03/noaa-office-of-space-commerces-crsra-division-seeks-input-on-satellite-disposal-debris-mitigation-regulations/>

⁴¹ *Supra* note 38.

⁴² *Supra* note 40, para 6.

⁴³ *Supra* note 36, para 3.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, para 2.

In an effort to address the regulatory gaps and overlap between federal agencies' regulation of orbital debris, a legislative proposal was introduced to establish a licensing process for private sector novel space activities, aligning with U.S. obligations under the OST.⁴⁵

5.2 Overarching Regulatory Frameworks: Mission Authorization

The current regulatory framework for the commercial space industry is thus fragmented among the FCC, NOAA, and the FAA, with NASA and the DOD playing advisory roles. In order to mitigate current challenges and anticipate future ones, a more seamless and flexible regulatory framework should be implemented. Proposed solutions include creating a "one-stop-shop" (e.g. a connected government model) where users connect through a central gateway to access services that may ultimately be provided by different government agencies.⁴⁶ This single government interface model could be implemented in a number of ways, for example, by consolidating regulatory functions within a single entity, or separating them with a primary agency designated to coordinate among the various entities.⁴⁷ However, concrete legislative action is needed in order to fully reallocate jurisdictional and regulatory authority. A critical legislative initiative aimed towards addressing this issue is mission authorization. It is, in brief, a proposed licensing regime that includes an authorization and supervision framework for novel space activities (e.g. new and emerging technologies, commercial habitats, in-space manufacturing, and on-orbit refueling).⁴⁸ Some experts argue that the DOT should be in charge of mission authorization, since it already regulates launch and reentry, while others advocate for the Department of Commerce (DOC).⁴⁹

It is important to note that mission authorization, or more specifically, filling the regulatory gaps currently present in the U.S.'s commercial space regulatory environment, is a binding international obligation under Article VI of the OST.⁵⁰ In 2015, Congress directed the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP), a division under NASA, to produce an assessment of the current and future commercial space activities and recommend a regulatory framework (for mission authorization) that would satisfy the U.S.'s OST obligations.⁵¹

Currently, four proposals for mission authorization frameworks have emerged from the White House's National Space Council, the House Science Committee, the National Space Council Users' Advisory Group, and the Senate Commerce Committee. The White House's policy guidance, titled the *United States Novel Space Activities Authorization and Supervision Framework*, was released in December 2023.⁵² The framework calls for interagency coordination and regulatory updates utilizing existing authorities to address mission authorization. More significantly, it splits the control for novel space activities between the DOC and DOT in order to take advantage of their regulatory expertise and competencies. The DOT would have

⁴⁵ *Ibid*, para. 1.

⁴⁶ Sorge, M. (2017, August). Commercial space activity and its impact on U.S. space debris regulatory structure (p. 5). The Aerospace Corporation. <https://aerospace.org/sites/default/files/2018-05/CommercialDebrisRegulation.pdf>

⁴⁷ *Ibid*.

⁴⁸ *Supra* note 44, para. 3.

⁴⁹ Smith, M. (2023, December 6). UAG endorses single agency for mission authorization. SpacePolicyOnline. <https://spacepolicyonline.com/news/uag-endorses-single-agency-for-mission-authorization/>

⁵⁰ Hitchens, T. (2023, November 29). White House plan for 'novel' space activities faces industry, Hill skepticism. Breaking Defense, para 5. <https://breakingdefense.com/2023/11/white-house-plan-for-novel-space-activities-faces-industry-hill-skepticism/>

⁵¹ Executive Office of the President, Office of Science and Technology Policy. (2016, April 4). *Report under Section 108 of the Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act*. https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/csla_report_4-4-16_final.pdf

⁵² White House. (2023, December). *United States Novel Space Activities Authorization and Supervision Framework*. The White House. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Novel-Space-Activities-Framework-2023.pdf>

authority over all human spaceflight activities, including missions to the moon, or other planets, as well as activities in Earth's orbit, and would license the transportation of materials in space and to the surface of the moon. The DOC would be granted more authority to regulate other uncrewed space activities (e.g. in-space servicing, assembly, and manufacturing, and active debris removal).

Critics of the White House's draft bill commented that its recommendations were out of step with both the House and Senate, and more importantly, the White House's draft bill split of control for novel space activities does nothing to streamline the regulation of the commercial space industry.⁵³ Additionally, as currently drafted, the current White House bill would allow government authorities such as the Department of Defense to put conditions on licenses to ensure national security, national interest, or space sustainability, causing challenges to arise regarding the interpretation of ambiguous language.⁵⁴

In contrast, representatives Frank Lucas (R-OK), House Science Committee Chairman, and Brian Babin (R-TX), Science Subcommittee on Space and Aeronautics chairman, introduced the Commercial Space Act of 2023.⁵⁵ The proposed Act seeks to establish a certification process for private spacecraft and space objects not currently licensed by U.S. agencies and would provide a statutory basis for regulating all commercial space activities, including debris mitigation. In stark contrast to the White House proposal, the Commercial Space Act would consolidate authority within the Department of Commerce, as opposed to splitting authorities between the DOT and NOAA. Additionally, the bill does not establish a traditional licensing regime; instead, it establishes a "passive process" that presumes approval unless the Department of Commerce denies an application within a 60-day timeframe.

Subsequently, in December 2023, the National Space Council's (NSC) User's Advisor group⁵⁶ released its own recommendations on a mission authorization framework to streamline the oversight of commercial space activities. Like the proposed Commercial Space Act, this framework aims to consolidate regulatory authority under a single agency, the DOC, addressing the fragmentation and overlap that currently characterize the U.S. orbital debris mitigation regime.

Lastly, the Senate Commerce Committee continues to work on developing its own commercial space bill. And, while the final draft has not been released, like its draft predecessors, the Senate's proposal will affirm the need for a mission authorization framework and is expected to consolidate mission authorization responsibilities within the Department of Commerce.

Thus, much of the holdup for mission authorization stems from a lack of consensus by policymakers. However, while much has been written about OST compliance, the U.S. has received no specific international criticism on the issue thus far. Moreover, the current, fragmented regulatory environment (existing as split jurisdiction between the FCC, FAA, and NOAA), still provides a robust mechanism of oversight for U.S. private sector space activities.⁵⁷ Furthermore, despite the lack of a concrete mission authorization framework, U.S. space companies have continued to produce technological innovation and increase the amount of capital flowing through the commercial space industry. In recent years, "Intuitive Machines made the first successful commercial lunar landing, Varda Space returned its orbital drug processing capsule, and SpaceX conducted multiple Starship test launches and its groundbreaking Polaris Dawn Mission, among other achievements from dozens of companies."⁵⁸ In considering these

⁵³ *Supra* note 50, para. 2-3.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ *Supra* note 44, para. 8.

⁵⁶ The UAG is a federal advisory committee established to ensure that the views of the private sector and nongovernmental commercial space stakeholders are provided to the NSC.

⁵⁷ *Supra* note 44, para. 4.

⁵⁸ *Supra* note 44, para. 5.

accomplishments, another solution would be to focus on streamlining existing processes in order to keep pace with the industry before turning to mission authorization.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE TRAJECTORY

Regardless, the fragmented regulatory environment in the United States is an issue that must be addressed in light of the increasing occupancy of outer space and the subsequent proliferation of debris. The U.S.'s current framework, which is spread across multiple agencies, including the FCC, FAA, and NOAA, has created inefficiencies and regulatory gaps that obstruct effective mitigation efforts. While each agency plays a vital role within its area of expertise, their overlapping jurisdictions and limited statutory scopes underscore the urgent need for a cohesive and streamlined regulatory approach.

The FCC has taken proactive steps to address orbital debris through updating its licensing requirements, but its unilateral rulemaking actions have sparked debates about statutory overreach and the need for greater interagency coordination. Similarly, the FAA's proposed rules on launch vehicle disposal and NOAA's evolving role in regulating remote sensing activities highlight the growing acknowledgement that orbital debris is a pressing concern that must be addressed. However, these efforts remain piecemeal, and without a unified mission authorization framework, the U.S. risks falling behind in fostering both a sustainable and competitive space industry.

To address these challenges, policymakers must prioritize regulatory clarity and interagency collaboration to create a seamless yet flexible framework for orbital debris mitigation. This regulatory clarity could even be something as limited as altering existing processes such that they are streamlined and as efficient as possible. Such a framework should also align with the best international practices, comply with international treaty obligations, incentivize innovation, and ensure the long-term sustainability of space activities. As the space economy continues to grow, the United States has a unique opportunity to lead by example in tackling orbital debris, safeguarding the future of space exploration, and maintaining its position as a global leader in the space industry.